

Münsteranian Tutorials on Nonlinear Science

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Overview of available auto07p Tutorials

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Abstract

The text briefly introduces the tutorials on numerical path-continuation within the “Münsteranian Torturials on Nonlinear Science”, a series of hands-on tutorials on the practical application of numerical and analytical methods for problems in soft matter and pattern formation. A recommended sequence of working through the tutorials is laid out and for each tutorial an abstract is given. The text contains hyperlinks to the individual tutorials on zenodo.

1 Introduction

The “Münsteranian Torturials on Nonlinear Science” represent a series of hands-on tutorials that shall facilitate the practical application of numerical path-continuation methods [1, 2] for problems in soft matter and pattern formation by lowering the entrance threshold for systems where side conditions as, e.g., conservation laws and projections due to translational invariance have to be taken into account. The presently available tutorials are based on the code package `auto07p` [3, 4, 5]. The diagram in Fig. 1 indicates the recommended sequence of working through them as it indicates intrinsic dependencies. For instance, `ACCHFP` introduces the continuation of fixed points corresponding to uniform steady states of Cahn-Hilliard and Allen-Cahn equations, while `ACCH` looks into heterogeneous steady states (patterns, structures) for the same equations employing periodic boundary conditions while `CHBC` considers an energetic bias at the boundaries. Alternatively, one may advance from `ACCH` towards `CCH` where the convective Cahn-Hilliard equation is considered, i.e., the resting clusters of `ACCH` begin to drift. Background information on the Cahn-Hilliard or Allen-Cahn equations and their derivation through nonequilibrium thermodynamics is given in the lectures [6, 7, 8] while a basic introduction of the numerical pseudo-arclength continuation method is discussed in the lecture [9].

If one wants to skip the quite simple case of fixed point continuation and directly start with the practical problem of drops of partially wetting liquid on a homogeneous substrate, use `SITDROP`. It is mathematically closely related to the Cahn-Hilliard equation considered in `ACCH` and determines families of sitting drop states and nucleation solutions. From there, one may advance either to the linear stability of these states with `LINDROP`, or to drops on a heterogeneous substrate with `HETDROP`, or to sliding drops on an incline with `SLIDROP`. Finally, `HETDRIV` and `ROTFFT` combine aspects of the latter two, investigating steady droplets on a heterogeneous inclined substrate and their stick-slipping motion beyond depinning. `DRIST` determines the linear stability of sliding drops by continuing the corresponding states, their eigenvalues and eigenfunctions in parameter space. This includes the determination of transversal instabilities of sliding liquid ridges.

The third set of tutorials consists at the moment of just one tutorial: `SH` determines periodic and localized steady states for the Swift-Hohenberg equation, a paradigmatic equation for the emergence of small-scale patterns [10, 11]. All available tutorials come with an extensive description where the studied equation, its implementation in `auto07p` and the various continuation runs are explained in detail. There, also further references are given. Below in Section 2, an abstract is given for each tutorial and a link is provided to its zenodo deposit containing the description and all needed files.

Note, however, that the tutorials assume that one has already installed `auto07p` (e.g., from <https://github.com/auto-07p/auto-07p>). After unpacking the code package into a directory “auto-07p-master”, follow the installation instructions on the first pages of the document `auto.pdf` (compile the `auto.tex` in directory `auto-07p-master/doc`). For instance, on linux/unix/macOS in directory `auto-07p-master` execute “./configure” and “make all”. Then include `auto07p` into

Figure 1: Tree diagram indicating the intrinsic dependencies of the available `auto07p` tutorials. From this a recommended sequence of working through them may be deduced.

your `PATH` (how to do this, depends on your operating system and shell, follow advice in `auto.pdf`). Before starting with the “Münsteranian Torturials”, read at least the first pages in the description `auto.pdf` and run some of the there described demos, for instance, “CUSP: A Tutorial Demo” (sec. 12.2, it shows how to continue fixed points of an ODE and is closely related to our `ACCHFP`), “EXP: Bratu’s Equation” (sec. 15.1, it shows how to obtain solutions to a boundary value problem), and “INT: Boundary and Integral Constraints” (sec. 15.2, it shows how to incorporate integral side conditions).

2 Tutorials

Here, we give the abstracts of all presently available `auto07p` tutorials.

2.1 ACCH

The tutorial explores steady states of the Allen-Cahn and the Cahn-Hilliard equation. These equations describe, e.g., the dynamics of concentration profiles of binary fluids or the dynamics of magnetisation profiles. You will calculate steady solutions in the case of periodic boundary conditions and continue them using domain size and mean concentration as main control parameters. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorial `ACCHFP`.

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2.2 ACCHFP

The tutorial explores the spatially uniform steady states of the Allen-Cahn equation. You will calculate steady states as a function of the continuation parameters temperature, chemical potential and external field. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after working through some of the tutorials that are part of `auto07p`.

Available at: [10.5281/zenodo.4546348](https://zenodo.org/record/4546348)

2.3 CCH

The tutorial explores the convective Cahn-Hilliard equation. Compared to the Cahn-Hilliard equation, it features an added lateral driving force. You will calculate stationary solutions representing drifting clusters and continue them using the driving strength as control parameter. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorial [ACCH](#).

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2.4 CHBC

The tutorial explores steady states of the Cahn-Hilliard equation with imposed non-periodic boundary conditions (energetic bias). You will calculate steady solutions on different branches continuing them in the energetic bias parameter. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorial [ACCH](#).

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2.5 DRIST

The tutorial employs continuation techniques to calculate selected stationary states of a driven thin-film equation together with their linear stability, i.e., steady profiles, their eigenvalues and eigenfunctions are continued in parallel. Retracing the various steps for this particular problem, you will be able to apply the technique to any equation of this form. Beside `auto07p` you will need `MatLab` to be able to use this tutorial. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorials [CCH](#) and/or [SLIDROP](#).

Available at: [10.5281/zenodo.4546407](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4546407)

2.6 HETDRIV

The tutorial explores steady drops on a substrate with spatially varying wettability under the additional influence of lateral driving. You will calculate these steady states as a function of the main control parameters domain size, heterogeneity contrast and driving strength. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorial [HETDROP](#).

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2.7 HETDROP

In the tutorial the dimensionless thin-film equation used in the tutorial [SITDROP](#) is adapted to a substrate with spatially varying wettability. In particular, the long-range contribution of the wetting energy is sinusoidally modulated. You will calculate steady states and their bifurcations that emerge when using the heterogeneity contrast as control parameter. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorial [SITDROP](#).

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2.8 LINDROP

The tutorial calculates the same 1d steady states as the tutorial [SITDROP](#), and additionally determines their linear stability (in 1d and 2d) with respect to time-dependent perturbations.

You will calculate the dispersion relation (growth rate over transversal wave number of the Plateau-Rayleigh instability of liquid ridges). Steady states and their stability are continued in various parameters. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorial [SITDROP](#).

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2.9 ROTFFTW

The tutorial explores the analogy between liquid films and drops on a rotating cylinder and substrates with spatially periodic one-dimensional wettability patterns. You will investigate depinning transitions that occur when the rotation speed of the cylinder is increased similar to the depinning of drops on heterogenous substrates. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorial [HETDROP](#).

Available at: [10.5281/zenodo.4546383](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4546383)

2.10 SH

The tutorial analyses the Swift-Hohenberg equation, a generic equation describing pattern formation close to a Turing instability. You will calculate uniform and periodic steady states. In particular, you will calculate periodic and localized states and determine their bifurcation behaviour. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after working through some of the tutorials that are part of `auto07p`.

Available at: [10.5281/zenodo.4546409](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4546409)

2.11 SITDROP

The tutorial explores an equation for steady drop- and hole-states derived from the dimensionless thin-film (or lubrication) equation. You will calculate steady solution of the equation by continuation in a number of different control parameters (domain size, liquid volume). The employed code package is `auto07p`.

Available at: [10.5281/zenodo.4546356](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4546356)

2.12 SLIDROP

The tutorial explores a dimensionless thin-film equation closely related to the one in the tutorial [SITDROP](#). Here, a lateral driving force is included and drops are examined that slide down an incline. You will calculate stationary states, i.e., steady states in a frame moving at a constant velocity (that is a nonlinear eigenvalue of the problem). The employed main control parameter is the inclination angle. The employed code package is `auto07p`. It is recommended to consider this tutorial after the tutorial [SITDROP](#).

Available at: [10.5281/zenodo.4546381](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4546381)

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